

In Memoriam

Prof. C.T. Akanbi (1954 – 2024)

The Ife Journal of Technology is deeply saddened to announce the passing of our esteemed former Editor-in-Chief (EiC), Prof. Charles T. Akanbi. Prof. Akanbi's distinguished tenure as EiC spanned from 2001 to 2024, a period during which the journal underwent significant modernization. Under his visionary leadership, the journal launched its website, which has been in continuous operation since 2002. Notably, IJT became one of the first Nigerian journals to adopt the PKP Open Journal Systems (OJS) management platform, enabling seamless online workflows for authors, reviewers, and editors—a practice that continues to this day. Prof. Akanbi was instrumental in elevating the journal's typesetting and formatting to a technically sophisticated and vibrant standard, making it one of the most distinctive academic publications in Nigeria. He also initiated the process of repositioning IJT as a truly international journal, broadening its scope and influence beyond its original affiliation with the Faculty of Technology at Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU).

Prof. Akanbi was a renowned scholar and academic. He earned his B.Sc. in Food Science and Technology from the University of Ife (now Obafemi Awolowo University) and went on to obtain an M.Sc. in Food Processing Engineering from the University of Reading in 1982, followed by a Ph.D. in Food Science from the University of Leeds in 1985. Upon completing his PhD, he joined the Department of Food Science and Technology, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife in 1986 where he quickly distinguished himself, rising to the rank of Professor of Food Processing in 2003.

Professor Akanbi's research centred on food processing, with particular emphasis on unit operations, including drying, rheology, and heat and mass transfer. His work led to innovations in the processing of indigenous Nigerian foods, including *kilishi*, yam, and pepper, among others. His scholarly output comprised over 70 journal articles and books.

As an academic leader and administrator, Prof. Akanbi's influence extended beyond research. He played a pivotal role in the development of the current Food Engineering B.Sc. program at OAU, variants of which have since been adopted by multiple Nigerian universities. His contributions to postgraduate engineering education culminated in his appointment as the Provost of the OAU Postgraduate College. During his tenure (2014-2016), he implemented significant reforms that enhanced academic rigor and streamlined administrative processes. His expertise was widely sought after, as evidenced by his participation in numerous national and international committees and panels.

Prof. Akanbi is survived by his devoted wife, children, and grandchildren. His legacy of excellence and dedication will continue to inspire the Ife Journal of Technology and all who had the privilege of knowing him.